

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

A STUDY ON PREVALENCE OF OBESITY AS A RISK FACTOR IN BREAST CANCER.

Vedasamhitha Ramavarapu, C.Subam Mahender, Srichurnam Sreekar

Malla Reddy Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Jawaharlal Nehru Technological University, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 28/07/2018

Available online

02/08/2018

Keywords

Obesity,
Breast Cancer,
Premenopausal,
Postmenopausal,
Metabolic Functions.

ABSTRACT

The prospects of breast carcinoma have been coupled with the increase in ubiquity of obesity over the last decade as a result of the hormonal and health complexities connected to it. More than two-thirds of female populace is being diagnosed with breast carcinoma who fall under either obese or overweight category, the association of which is found to be progressive each year. There is an affirmable increase in the risk of breast carcinoma among postmenopausal women is high when put aside with premenopausal women, with respect to its incidence in India. In most meta-analysis, systematic reviews and observational studies, obesity has been proved to be a considerable risk factor. Obesity is incident in more or less 60% of patients at diagnosis of breast carcinoma and an additional 60-75% gain in weight is observed in patients throughout the treatment. Obesity is related to higher levels of insulin and other hormones in both pre and post-menopausal women. Apart from other metabolic hormones associated with cancer and its recurrence, insulin secretion and connected proteins have long been associated with the increased risk of cancer and also its recurrence. With the leading change in food patterns and the lifestyle changes, resulted in a declining physical activity and increasing BMI in an average human population, over the past two decades. A major percentage of studies indicate that being obese can be a poor prognostic factor and is related to less favorable nodal status in addition to increased risk of contralateral illness, recurrence, co-morbidities and overall mortality.

Corresponding author

Vedasamhitha Ramavarapu

Department of Pharm. D (Doctor of Pharmacy),
Malla Reddy Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences
Jawaharlal Nehru Technological University,
Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

Please cite this article in press as **Vedasamhitha Ramavarapu et al.** A Study on Prevalence of Obesity as a Risk Factor in Breast Cancer. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2018:8(07).

Copy right © 2018 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

www.iajpr.com

INTRODUCTION

Despite the notable advancements in the medical field, breast carcinoma remains a ubiquitous condition amongst populace worldwide. About 25% (1.67 million) of new cancer cases being diagnosed annually consist of female-specific cancer cases, particularly breast carcinomas. The number of cases reported from developed regions (794000) is notably less significant than the cases reported from the less developed regions (883000 cases) [1].

With the leading change in food patterns and the lifestyle changes, resulted in a declining physical activity and increasing BMI in an average human population, over the past two decades [6]. Obesity among women with breast carcinoma in the premenopausal stages was inverse in various analysis [2, 3, 4, 5]. There is an affirmable increase risk of breast cancer in postmenopausal women when compared to premenopausal women, with respect to its incidence in India. When compared to Caucasians, Indians were found to be having higher body fat percentage, apart from a high prevalence of central obesity among Indian population [7].

In an age-adjusted study data for obesity (BMI $>_{\geq}$ 30.0 kg/m²) the demonstration of prevalence is 34.9% among adults aged 20 or above when staged with overweight plus obese populace (BMI $>_{\geq}$ 25.0 kg/m²) which comprises of 68.5% prevalence. In most meta-analysis, systematic reviews and observational studies [6,7], obesity has been proved to be a considerable risk factor. More than two-thirds of female populace is being diagnosed with breast carcinoma who fall under either obese or overweight category, the association of which is found to be progressive every year [6,7].

The risk of breast cancer has been coupled with the prevalence of obesity over the last decade as a result of the hormonal and health complexities connected to it. Increased risk of invasive breast cancer is associated with obesity in postmenopausal women [8,9].

Obesity is incident in more or less 60% of patients at diagnosis of breast carcinoma and an additional 60-75% gain in weight is observed in patients throughout the treatment [10]. A major percentage of studies indicate that being obese can be a poor prognostic factor and is related to less favorable nodal status in addition to increased risk of contralateral illness, recurrence, co-morbidities and overall mortality [11]. Obesity is related to higher levels of insulin and other hormones in both pre and post-menopausal women. Apart from other metabolic hormones associated with cancer and its recurrence, insulin secretion and connected proteins have been associated with the increased risk of occurrence of cancer and also its recurrence [12]. In premenopausal women, increased levels of IGF-1 [insulin secretion like growth factor] are associated with increased risk of carcinoma, and this secretion contains a central role in disease development and progression [13].

Despite the relativity of BMI higher than 30 kg/m² as a risk factor of higher incidence of breast carcinoma in postmenopausal stages of women [13] many analytical studies have show that in contrast to this there is a declining risk in premenopausal stages of Asian and Caucasian populations [14,15].

Increased prospects of breast cancer are seen in women with high BMI especially in the postmenopausal state [16]. The effects of central obesity on premenopausal women inclined more towards the ethnic status of the populace [16].

For instance, a prospective increase of 12% was observed with every 5-unit jump in BMI, most of analysis proving postmenopausal population to be more prevalent [17].

40-20% increase in prospects of erupting breast cancer was noticed amid the postmenopausal population in contrast with normal weight population [18].

Although breast cancer among men is a rarity, the association of hormonal imbalances and complexities following obesity have made it a prevalent risk factor among male breast carcinomas too [19]. Obesity is often compared to metabolism which widespread in recent times and it is associated with higher risk of postmenopausal breast carcinoma [20]. Many studies have correlated obesity harmoniously with postmenopausal carcinoma of breast [21].

After considering these observations, the study of the relativity to obesity and breast cancer proves to be an evident factor, if this is properly understood factor, there can be more preventive measures to avoid any complications in the approach towards disease management.

METHODOLOGY:

The study was carried out in two tertiary care hospitals located in Hyderabad, India. The prime department of the study consist of Surgical and Medical Oncology. The design of the study is a prospective observational study, it was carried out for a period of six months. The sample size concurring to be 173 Case studies, the participants in the study consist of outpatient and inpatient populace in the hospital.

STUDY DESIGN:

The study structure is carried out as retrospective and prospective observational studies to analyze the relativity of obesity as a risk factor of breast carcinoma. Taking body mass indices on diagnosis into consideration.

STUDY PERIOD:

The study period is planned in the timeline of July 2017 to February 2018.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

Patient population consisting of conditions like the following

- Breast carcinoma
- Recurrent Breast carcinoma
- Metastatic Breast carcinoma
- Patients undergoing Adjuvant and Neoadjuvant chemotherapy.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

Patient population with conditions like

- Fibroadenomas.
- Cystic mass.
- Hematomas.
- Fat necrosis.
- Hamartoma.

Statistical analysis:

Statistical analysis was produced using an analytical tool Minitab[®] 17.2. The descriptive statistics were presented either as Mean $\pm$ SD, Standard error mean, Variance, Skewness, Median, Q3, Maximum. The graphical and descriptive statistical analysis was done for Demographic data, clinical staging, the presence of recurrence, treatment types and menopausal status of the subjects.

RESULTS**Gender:**

Among 173 breast carcinoma patients, 1.7% of rarity for male breast carcinoma cases was seen, 98.3% were female breast carcinoma cases. The pie-chart obtained from the statistics is shown in Graph 1.

Graph 1. Pie chart of Gender Prevalence.

Descriptive statistics of age:

The data for 173 breast cancer patients was collected from a tertiary care hospital and the Mean $\pm$ SD of the age of the subjects was found to be 51.15 ± 12.88 years with an age range of 18-81. The minimum, median, and maximum ages were derived as 18.00, 52.00, 81.00. A standard error of 0.979 was found in the data. The obtained descriptive analysis is displayed in Table 1.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics for age.

Variable	N	Mean	Std. error Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Q1	Median	Q3	Maximum
Age	173	51.15	0.979	12.88	18.00	43.0	52.00	60.0	81.00

The population from the data was divided into age groups from below 30 to above 60 with the class interval of 15 in each class in the two groups between the above-mentioned class. This revealed that major percentage of the population with breast cancer lies between menopausal or post-menopausal stages of life. The simple histogram chart of the same is shown in Graph 2.

Graph 2. Populace in different age groups.**Obesity:**

The population was categorized using the NIH chart given as classification of overweight and obesity by BMI descriptive statistics were analysed for the prevalence of obese and overweight patients. The tabulation of which is shown in Table 2 and Graph 3.

Table 2. The population of Obese patients according to NIH classification of BMI.

NIH Classification	Count	Total percentage
Normal	94	54.34
Overweight	45	26.01
Obesity Class I	19	10.98
Obesity Class II	9	5.20
Obesity Class III	6	3.47
Total	173	100

Graph 3. Pie chart for population of Obese patients according to NIH classification of BMI.

One sample t-test was performed to analyze the significance of obesity in breast cancer patients. A p-value showing 0.004 less than 0.05 was obtained indicating that obesity remains significant factor in breast cancer populace, considering the hypothesis μ of BMI 25. The analytical values are represented in Table 4.

Table 4. One sample t-test.

N	Mean	Std. Deviation	SE Mean	95%lower bound	T	P
173	26.072	5.219	0.397	25.416	2.70	0.004

The descriptive statistics for the BMI showing Mean as 26.7, Standard error mean as 0.39, Variance as 27.23, Standard deviation as 5.21 have been presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics for BMI.

Variable	N	Mean	SE Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Q1	Median	Q3	Maximum
BMI	173	26.07	0.39	5.21	18.90	22.51	23.92	28.67	42.42

DISCUSSION

The Mean $\pm$ SD of the age of 173 subjects was found to be 51.15 ± 12.88 years with an age range of 18-81. The minimum, median and the maximum ages were derived as 18.00, 52.00, 81.00.

Obesity is incident in more or less 60% of patients at diagnosis of breast carcinoma and an additional 60-75% gain in weight is observed in patients throughout the treatment. A major percentage of studies indicate that being obese can be a poor prognostic factor and is related to less favorable nodal status in addition to increased risk of contralateral illness, recurrence, co-morbidities and overall mortality [7].

There were 26.01% of patients falling under the category of overweight, 10.98% and 5.20% falling under obesity class I and class II, and obesity class III being 3.47% of the considered population. The mean BMI being 26.7 Standard error mean is 0.39.

One sample t-test was performed to analyze the significance of overweight and obesity in breast cancer populace. A p-value showing 0.004 less than 0.05 was obtained indicating that obesity remains significant factor in breast cancer populace.

CONCLUSION

The study shows a significant prevalence of obesity in breast cancer patients amongst the considered population.

Overweight and obese populations shows more inclination towards the risk of breast carcinoma, probably due to decreased metabolism or sedentary lifestyles.

Taking appropriate measures to acquire an optimal body mass index (BMI) can be considered as a vital consideration to avoid the occurrence overlapping breast carcinomas. For which some or moderate physical exercise can be adapted on a daily basis. And avoiding a sedentary lifestyle can be advised as it can lead to obesity and hormonal imbalances.

Study Limitations:

Being a study carried out for a short duration of six months. The limitations for analysis were concluded to be:

- A population of 173 patients.
- Study site constrained to only one two tertiary care hospitals in a large city.

All of which contributed to a small sample size and constrained to study concerned to one populace.

Conflict of interest:

There were no conflicts of interest amongst the authors.

REFERENCES

1. Malvia, S., Bagadi, S. A., Dubey, U. S. and Saxena, S. (2017), Epidemiology of breast cancer in Indian women. *Asia-Pac J Clin Oncol*, 13: 289–295.
2. Michels KB, Terry KL, Willett WC. Longitudinal study on the role of body size in premenopausal breast cancer. *Arch Intern Med*.2006;166:2395- 2402.
3. Berstad P, Coates RJ, Bernstein L, et al. A case- control study of body mass index and breast cancer risk in white and African- American women. *Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev*.2010;19:1532- 1544.
4. White AJ, Nichols HB, Bradshaw PT, Sandler DP. Overall and central adiposity and breast cancer risk in the Sister Study. *Cancer*.2015;121:3700- 3708.
5. Harris HR, Willett WC, Terry KL, Michels KB. Body fat distribution and risk of premenopausal breast cancer in the Nurses' Health Study II. *J Natl Cancer Inst*. 2011;103:273- 278.
6. Neuhauser ML, Aragaki AK, Prentice RL, et al. Overweight, Obesity and Postmenopausal Invasive Breast Cancer Risk. *JAMA oncology*. 2015;1(5):611-621.
7. Wen M, Kowaleski-Jones L. The Built Environment and Risk of Obesity in the United States: Racial-Ethnic Disparities. *Health & place*. 2012;18(6):1314-1322.
8. Kuczmarski, R. J. & Flegal, K. M. Criteria for the definition of overweight in transition: background and recommendations for the United States. *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.* 72, 1074–1081 (2000).
9. Seidell, J. & Rissanen, A. in *Handbook of Obesity: Etiology and Pathophysiology* (eds. Bray, G. & Bouchard, C.) 93–107 (Marcel Dekker, New York, 2004).
10. Flegal, K. M., Carroll, M. D., Ogden, C. L. & Johnson, C. L. Prevalence and trends in obesity among US adults, 1999–2000. *JAMA* 288 1723–1727 (2002).
11. Ballard-Barbash, R. & Swanson, C. A. Body weight: estimation of risk for breast and endometrial cancer. *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.* 63(Suppl. 3), 437–441 (1996).
12. Hulka BS, Moorman PG. Breast cancer: hormones and other risk factors. *Maturitas*. 2001; 38: 103- 113; discussion 113- 116.
13. Ligibel J. Obesity and breast cancer *Oncology (Williston Park)*. 2011 Oct;25(11):994- 1000.
14. Ziegler RG, Hoover RN, Pike MC, Hildesheim A, Nomura AM, West DW, Wu-Williams AH, Kolonel LN, Horn-Ross PL, Rosenthal JF, et al: Migration patterns and breast cancer risk in Asian-American women. *J Natl Cancer Inst*. 1993, 85: 1819-1827.
15. Calle, E. E., Miracle-McMahill, H. L., Thun, M. J. & Heath, C. W. Jr. Estrogen replacement therapy and risk of fatal colon cancer in a prospective cohort of postmenopausal women. *J. Natl Cancer Inst*. 87, 517–523 (1995).
16. Jemal A, Center MM, Desantis C, Ward EM. Global patterns of cancer incidence and mortality rates and trends. *Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev*. 2010; 19: 1893- 1907.

17. Althuis MD, Dozier JD, Anderson WF, Devesa SS, Brinton LA. Global trends in breast cancer incidence and mortality 1973- 1997. *Int J Epidemiol.* 2005; 34: 405- 412.
18. Colditz GA, Sellers TA, Trapido E. Epidemiology- identifying the causes and preventability of cancer? *Nat Rev.* 2006; 6: 75- 83.
19. Mokdad, A. H. *et al.* Prevalence of obesity, diabetes, and obesity-related health risk factors, 2001. *JAMA* 289, 76–79 (2003).
20. Grundy SM. Metabolic syndrome pandemic. *Arterioscler Thromb Vasc Biol.* 2008;28:629- 636.
21. Agnoli C, Berrino F, Abagnato CA, et al. Metabolic syndrome and postmenopausal breast cancer in the ORDET cohort: a nested case- control study. *Nutr Metab Cardiovasc Dis.* 2010; 20:41 48.

54878478451180714

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

Convenient online manuscript submission

Access Online first

Double blind peer review policy

International recognition

No space constraints or color figure charges

Immediate publication on acceptance

Inclusion in **ScopeMed** and other full-text repositories

Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

